

MANDA SATVA: A MODIFIED PHARMACEUTICAL PREPARATION OF CLASSICAL MANDA

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ABSTRACT

Ayurveda gives prime importance to *Ahara* in both preventive and curative healthcare. Among the various dietary preparations described in classical Ayurvedic literature, *Manda* is considered one of the lightest and most easily digestible preparations. It is commonly prescribed in conditions associated with impaired digestion, fever, debility, dehydration and during post-therapeutic recovery. Modern pharmaceutical adaptation of classical *Ayurvedic* preparations is essential for improving stability, acceptability, portability and patient compliance. In this context, *Manda Satva* is a modified pharmaceutical preparation developed from classical *Manda* by concentration, drying, and powdering techniques. The present article discusses the classical concept of *Manda*, the rationale for modification, pharmaceutical preparation of *Manda Satva*, *Ayurvedic* properties, therapeutic applications, pharmaceutical significance, and a modern nutritional perspective. The article also emphasizes the importance of integrating classical dietary wisdom with contemporary pharmaceutical approaches.

KEYWORDS: *Manda*, *Manda Satva*, *Pathya Kalpana*, *Ayurveda*, *Satva Kalpana*, Pharmaceutical Modification.

INTRODUCTION

Ayurveda considers *Ahara* as one of the three major supports of life (*Trayopastambha*)⁽¹⁾, the other two being *Nidra* and *Brahmacharya*. A proper diet is not only a necessity for survival but also a therapeutic tool for the treatment of diseases. Classical Ayurvedic texts extensively describe several dietary preparations suitable for different stages of digestion and disease conditions.

Among these, *Pathya Kalpana* occupies an important place. These preparations are specifically designed to.

- Support weakened digestion
- Provide nourishment
- Restore physiological balance
- Promote recovery

Classical *pathya* preparations include.

- a. *Manda*
- b. *Peya*
- c. *Vilepi*
- d. *Yavagu*

In present pharmaceutical practice, classical formulations are often modified to improve.

- Shelf life
- Stability
- Ease of administration
- Transportability
- Patient convenience

Manda Satva is one such modified preparation developed from classical *Manda*. It represents the concentrated starch-rich nutritive essence of rice gruel filtrate processed into a stable powdered form.

Historical and Classical Background of *Manda*

The concept of *Manda* is described in classical Ayurvedic literature under *Anna Kalpana* and *Pathya Kalpana*. According to the *Charaka Samhita*, light dietary preparations are recommended for diseases associated with weakened *Agni*. According to *Ashtanga Hridaya*, *Manda* is *Laghu*, easily digestible, increases *Agni*, suitable for illness and recovery.

- Manda is defined as “*Sikthairvirahito mandah*”, which means the liquid part fully devoid of solid portion, is considered here as manda.^[2] The supernatant liquid portion of rice boiled with 14 parts of water is called as *Manda*. This liquid is administered by adding the required quantity of *Shunthi* and *Saindhava* for better therapeutic efficacy.^[3]

- **Pharmacological actions of *Manda***

It is *Agni dipaka*, *Vata anulomana*, *Srotomridukara* and *Sweda kaaraka*. It can be advised for those who are under *Langhana*, *Virechana* and *Snehana* types of treatment. As it nourishes the body very quickly. It is called *Pranadharaka*.^[4,5]

- **Preparation of Classical *Manda***

It is prepared using one part of rice and fourteen parts of water. The rice is first cleaned thoroughly and washed properly, after which the required quantity of water is added. The mixture is then cooked over mild heat until the rice is completely cooked. Once cooking is completed, the supernatant liquid is carefully decanted and filtered to obtain a clear liquid preparation known as *Manda*.^[6]

- **Types^[7]**

1. *Astaguna Manda*

Manda prepared with eight ingredients such as *Dhanyaka*, *Trikatu*, *Saindhava lavana*, *Mudga*, *Tandula*, and fried *Hingu*. It acts as *Deepana*, *Basti sodhana*, *Rakta vardhana* and helps in *Jwara*, alleviates dosha.

2. *Vatya Manda*

Manda is prepared with fried barley, and it acts as *Kapha*, *Pitta hara*, *Kantya*, *Raktapitta hara*.

3. *Laja Manda*

Manda prepared with soaked and fried *Laja*. It acts as *kapha pitta hara* and *Grahi* and pacifies *Trishna*, *Jwara*.

- **Properties of *Manda***

1. *Rasa - Madhura*
2. *Guna - Laghu, Mridu*

- **Materials Required**

Table 1: Materials Required for *Manda Satva*.

S.No	Material	Purpose
1	Rice	Raw material
2	Water	Extraction medium
3	Filtration cloth	Separation
4	Heating apparatus	Concentration
5	Double-boiling setup	Controlled heating
6	Stainless steel vessel	Processing
7	Khalva yantra / Mixer grinder	Powdering

Method of Preparation of *Manda Satva*

Step 1: Preparation of *Manda*

The preparation begins with cleaning, drying, and pounding the rice properly, after which fourteen parts of

3. *Virya-Sheeta*
4. *Karma - Deepana, Pachana, Trishna Nigrahana, Vata anulomana*

- **Therapeutic Uses of *Manda***

1. *Jwara*
2. *Agnimandya*
3. Post *Panchakarma* Care (initial stage of *Samsarjana Krama*)

- **Need for Pharmaceutical Modification**

Despite its therapeutic importance, classical *Manda* possesses certain limitations.

- * Short shelf life
- * Spoils quickly because of chances of fermentation and microbial contamination.
- * Requires fresh preparation every time before use.
- * Poor portability.
- * Not convenient for large-scale pharmaceutical use and packaging.
- * To be consumed in a large dose.

Modern pharmaceutical adaptation aims to preserve the therapeutic and nutritional essence while improving its utility (by reducing dosage and improving palatability). Therefore, *Manda* was modified into *Manda Satva*, a concentrated powder form.

➤ **CONCEPT OF *MANDA SATVA***

In Ayurvedic pharmaceuticals, the term “*Satva*” generally denotes the essence, active fraction, or concentrated nutritive component of a substance. Accordingly, *Manda Satva* can be understood as the concentrated starch-rich nutritive essence obtained from *Manda*.

Definition of *Manda Satva*

Manda Satva is a modified pharmaceutical preparation prepared by concentrating the filtrate of classical *Manda*, followed by drying and powdering to obtain its nutritive starch essence.

water is added. The mixture is then cooked over a mild flame until the rice is completely cooked. Once cooking is completed, the supernatant liquid is carefully decanted and filtered. The clear filtrate obtained from this process

is known as Manda.

Step 2: Collection of Filtrate

The prepared filtrate is collected and subjected for further processing.

Step 3: Re-boiling

The collected filtrate is again heated over a mild flame. As the evaporation proceeds gradually, the preparation becomes increasingly viscous and attains a semi-solid consistency.

Step 4: Double Boiling Method

In the double boiling method, the semisolid preparation is kept in one vessel, which is placed inside or above another

vessel containing water. Heat is applied to the outer vessel, and the preparation gets heated indirectly through the hot water. The process is continued until the material becomes completely dry.

Step 5: Powdering

After drying, the solid mass is collected, crushed well using a *Khalva yantra* / mixer grinder and sieved to obtain fine powder. It is collected and stored in an airtight container. The final product obtained is known as *Manda Satva*.

Figure: Method of Preparation of Manda Satva.

Manda Satva

Table 2: Organoleptic Characteristics of *Manda Satva*.

S.No	Parameter	Observation
1	Appearance	Fine powder
2	Color	White to cream
3	Texture	Smooth
4	Taste	Mild/bland
5	Odour	Characteristic rice odour

Table 3: Pharmaceutical Significance.

S.No	Pharmaceutical Step	Importance
1	Filtration	Removal of coarse particles
2	Re-boiling	Concentration
3	Double boiling	Protection from charring
4	Drying	To remove moisture
5	Powdering	Ease of administration

- **Ayurvedic Analysis of *Manda Satva***

Table 4: Ayurvedic properties of *Manda Satva*.

S.No	Ayurvedic Property	Effect
1	<i>Laghu</i>	Easy to digestion
2	<i>Brimhana</i>	Nourishment
3	<i>Balya</i>	Enhance the strength
4	<i>Pitta Shamana</i>	Cooling effect
5	<i>Trishna Nigrahana</i>	Reduces thirst

Therapeutic Applications**1. Jwara**

Manda Satva has laghu guna, deepana, *Swedosanjana* properties making it useful for jwara.

2. Agnimandya

Manda Satva is light and easy to digest, making it useful in Agnimandya.

3. Convalescence (Recovering phase)

Manda Satva is useful during recovery from chronic illness, surgery, *Panchakarma* procedures, and states of physical exhaustion, as it helps restore strength and nourishment.

4. Pediatric Nutrition

Children with weak digestive capacity may tolerate

Manda Satva well because of its light and easily digestible properties.

5. Geriatric Nutrition

It is also suitable for elderly individuals with reduced *Agni*, poor appetite, and weakened digestion.

➤ Modern Scientific Perspective

From a contemporary scientific perspective, *Manda Satva* can be considered a starch-rich nutritional preparation predominantly composed of easily digestible carbohydrates. Rice starch serves as a major source of dietary energy and is readily digested and absorbed in the gastrointestinal tract. Due to low fat content and mild protein content, it provides rapid caloric support without imposing a significant digestive burden. Its easily digestible nature may be beneficial in individuals with

impaired digestion, fever, gastrointestinal sensitivity, and during recovery from chronic illness.^[8,9] Owing to its light and easily absorbable nature, it may also be useful in pediatric and geriatric nutritional support. Manda Satva may be viewed as a readily available nutritional preparation that provides energy while remaining gentle on the digestive system.

➤ Comparative Analysis

Table 5: Comparison between Classical Manda and Manda Satva.

Parameter	Classical Manda	Manda Satva
Form	Liquid	Powder
Shelf life	Short	Longer
Preparation	Fresh daily	Ready to use
Portability	Difficult	Easy
Stability	Less	More

➤ Scope for Future Research

Further studies may be conducted regarding.

- Physicochemical analysis
- Nutritional profiling
- Stability studies
- QC-Parameters.
- Clinical efficacy studies

➤ DISCUSSION

The adaptation of classical Ayurvedic formulations is necessary to address current healthcare needs while preserving their therapeutic value. Manda Satva serves as an example of how traditional dietary preparations can be pharmaceutically modified without compromising their essential benefits.

The formulation retains the therapeutic qualities of classical Manda while minimising practical limitations such as poor shelf life and difficulty in storage. The powdered form of Manda Satva offers additional pharmaceutical advantages such as ease of administration, dose standardisation, improved stability and reduced risk of microbial contamination.

Manda Satva can be viewed as a link between classical Pathya Kalpana and modern nutritional pharmaceuticals (nutraceuticals). Owing to its simplicity, affordability, and easy digestibility, it may have potential applications in clinical nutrition and supportive care.

➤ CONCLUSION

Manda Satva is a modified pharmaceutical preparation derived from classical *Manda* through concentration, drying, and powdering processes. It preserves the therapeutic and nutritional value of *Manda* while improving stability, portability, and convenience. The preparation is light, easy to digest and nourishing. It may serve as a beneficial supportive preparation for fever, convalescence, digestive disorders, pediatric and geriatric nutrition. Further pharmaceutical standardization and clinical validation may help establish

Manda Satva as an effective Ayurvedic nutritional preparation in contemporary healthcare practice.

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